

Understanding sediment wash-off in road drainage systems under intense rainfall and high sediment masses: Insights from a large-scale modeling facility

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HIGHLIGHTS

- RDS wash-off under intense rainfall and high masses in large-scale tests.
- 1:1 scale modeling facility precisely measures RDS wash-off phenomenon.
- Intervention sequence for fine RDS pollution control: manhole > gully pot > roadway.
- RDS mass limits are determined to suggest improvements in road drainage components.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this paper is to analyze, through a unique large-scale modeling facility, the RDS wash-off under various scenarios of intense rainfall and high RDS masses. A 1:1 scale physical modeling facility was used to allow precise measurement of the RDS wash-off phenomenon under two different rainfall intensities (30/50 mm/h) and three initial RDS masses (100/150/200 g/m²). The accumulated and discharged masses of RDS in the different components of the modeling facility (roadway/RW, gully pot/GP and manhole/MH) were collected at the end of the wash-off simulations. The results suggested the following sequence of intervention in the components of the drainage system to control pollution associated with fine RDS (< 63 μm): MH (59.2 %) > GP (31.2 %) > RW (9.6 %). The wash-off simulations suggested the following maximum (30/68 g/m²), minimum (16/38 g/m²) and minimum (2.15/2.61 g/m²) limits on the mass of RDS remaining on the RW, removed by the GP and discharged into the MH, respectively. These mass limits were relevant to understand the RDS behavior and to suggest improvement strategies for the RW cleaning systems (coarse/fine fractions washed-off: 80.3/81.7 %), GPs (coarse/fine fractions removed: 75.3/49.6 %) and MHs (coarse/fine fractions discharged: 5/32.1 %). Finally,

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the results suggested that the size fractions $<63 \mu\text{m}$ and between 500 and $1000 \mu\text{m}$ were representative of the wash-off for the finest and coarsest fractions of the RDS, respectively.

1. Introduction

The wash-off of road-deposited sediments (RDSs) by surface runoff poses a widespread challenge in urban areas, occasioning detrimental consequences for the environment, infrastructure and public well-being (Martínez et al., 2024; Yarmoshenko et al., 2020). Loaded with a spectrum of contaminants including oils, heavy metals, nutrients and various chemicals, RDSs washed-off by runoff from urban roadways (RWs) become vectors of pollution (Ghosh and Maiti, 2018). Upon reaching urban water bodies, these sediment-laden runoffs exacerbate water quality degradation and impose harmful impacts on aquatic ecosystems (Ferreira et al., 2018). Diffuse pollution from urban road runoff emerges as a crucial driver of environmental degradation and water quality decline (Müller et al., 2020). Moreover, the accretion of RDSs within storm drainage infrastructure poses a dual threat, impeding flow and increasing the susceptibility of urban areas to inundation during intense rainfall events (Wang et al., 2017). Mitigating the buildup of RDSs necessitates recurrent maintenance efforts, incurring substantial financial burdens for municipal authorities (Haynes et al., 2020).

The phenomenon of RDS wash-off entailed the removal of sediment from road surfaces through the action of rainfall and runoff. Two primary processes governed RDS wash-off from impervious surfaces: RDS buildup during dry weather and RDS removal via rainfall and runoff action (Li et al., 2023a). The mobilization of RDS was driven by two factors: the impact energy of raindrops and the shear stress of surface flow, with the latter being particularly sensitive to surface slope (Kinnell, 2022). Studies have noted the direct correlation between rainfall intensity and the extent of RDS wash-off by road runoff, wherein intense rainfall led to accelerated runoff flows and increased potential for road erosion (Naves et al., 2020). Moreover, the characteristics of RDS, including composition and particle size distribution (PSD), influenced its susceptibility to wash-off by runoff (dos Santos et al., 2019). Fine, loose RDSs were more readily mobilized compared to coarser, compacted RDSs (Rivers et al., 2021; Russell et al., 2019). Topography and road design also influenced RDS wash-off, with road slope and surface configuration affecting runoff velocity and direction, thereby influencing wash-off spatial distribution (Chen et al., 2022).

Forecasting RDS wash-off masses using rainfall-runoff modeling systems played a key role in the advancement of urban drainage systems (Hu and Zhao, 2022). The accurate modeling of RDS wash-off was crucial for informed decision-making regarding sediment transport and water quality. However, modeling RDS wash-off was a complex task due to the variable nature of parameters such as rainfall (duration and intensity), catchment surface (roughness, slope and drainage system components) and particle characteristics (RDS mass and PSD). Modeling approaches for RDS wash-off on roads ranged from simple event mean concentration (EMC) methods to more sophisticated build-up and wash-off models (Faisal et al., 2022). Numerous empirical equations and models had conventionally been employed for modeling RDS wash-off phenomenon (Egodawatta et al., 2007; Muthusamy et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the predictive capacity of these simplified models remained relatively limited (Gorgoglione et al., 2019), primarily due to challenges in accurately measuring input parameters such as initial RDS mass and characteristics, compounded by their inability to address spatial and RDS heterogeneities. In recent years, the adoption of physically-based wash-off formulations emerged as an alternative to empirical equations (Hong et al., 2016; Naves et al., 2020a). This provided a means to incorporate spatial variabilities and simulate main wash-off mechanisms, including particle detachment induced by raindrop impacts or runoff shear, and particle transportation and deposition. The transition to this type of modeling facility required accurate

information for its development and validation, which incorporated a larger number of input variables to faithfully represent surface flow dynamics (Addison-Atkinson et al., 2024).

Several studies have utilized rainfall simulation facilities to analyze the RDS wash-off. Egodawatta et al. (2007) employed a rainfall simulator with intensities ranging from 20 to 133 mm/h, consisting of three nozzles (Veejet 80,100) connected to a bar and located 2.5 m above ground level. The nozzle bar oscillated in both directions with controlled speed and delay. This rainfall simulator used demineralized water to replicate the quality of natural rainfall. The objective of these researchers was to mathematically interpret the wash-off of pollutants from road surfaces. Zhao et al. (2018) used a simulator that considered rainfall intensities between 29.9 and 80.7 mm/h, an initial RDS mass of 20 g/m^2 and a surface area of 3.3 m^2 ($1.5 \text{ m} \times 2.2 \text{ m}$). Two devices with four nozzles (Veejet 80,100) were used, positioned at a height of 2.5 m and provided uniform rainfall at 0.04 MPa. The aim of these researchers was to study the role of surface roughness on the buildup and wash-off of RDS. Muthusamy et al. (2018) utilized a rainfall simulator with the following technical characteristics: rainfall intensities between 33 and 155 mm/h, initial RDS mass between 50 and 200 g/m^2 , road slope between 2 and 16 %, surface area of 1 m^2 ($1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$) and nozzles (1/4-HH-14 W FullJet from Spraying Systems Co.) located at a height of 2.2 m above ground level. Al Ali et al. (2017) used a portable simulator to continuously monitor the wash-off flow and turbidity at the outlet of an urban road surface. The technical characteristics of the simulator were as follows: rainfall intensity of 120 mm/h, wash-off duration of 10 min, initial RDS mass between 11 and 27.4 g/m^2 , surface area of 1 m^2 ($1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$) and nozzles located at a height of 1.6 m above ground level. However, few studies have simulated the RDS wash-off in a large-scale modeling facility that integrates the main components of a road drainage system. Thus, in our study, the modeling facility used included the following components: roadway, curb, sidewalk, gully pot and manhole. The parameterization of the experiments performed will also allow modeling specialists to use them as calibration scenarios for more complex numerical modeling.

In this study, the selection of intense rainfalls for simulations in a large-scale modeling facility was fundamental to understanding RDS wash-off dynamics under extreme weather conditions. These intensities represented common yet challenging scenarios in urban environments, where intense rainfall could significantly affect the efficiency of drainage systems (Neupert et al., 2021). By simulating these conditions, the study aimed to provide insights into RDS transport and buildup behavior for the design of resilient urban drainage infrastructure. Moreover, the choice of high RDS masses was essential to evaluate the performance of drainage systems under varying sediment loads. These values were selected based on observed urban sedimentation rates (Loganathan et al., 2013; Romero-Barreiro et al., 2015), ensuring that the simulations reflected realistic and severe conditions. High RDS masses could exacerbate the clogging of drainage systems, leading to increased flood risks and maintenance costs (García-Haba et al., 2023). This innovative approach, which combined intense rainfalls and high RDS masses, allowed for a comprehensive assessment of the capacities of urban road drainage systems, for example, under a scenario of increasing urbanization and climate change. The findings are likely to contribute to the development of more effective RDS management strategies, enhancing urban resilience to extreme weather and high RDS mass events. The insights gained from this study will also be relevant for urban planners and engineers, providing a solid foundation for future advancements in the design and maintenance of road drainage systems.

In this context, the main objective of this paper is to analyze, through a unique large-scale modeling facility, the wash-off of RDS under various

scenarios of intense rainfall and high sediment masses. The experiments presented herein offer a significant opportunity to advance our comprehension of the processes governing RDS wash-off. This research holds practical relevance for the following reasons: (1) the utilization of a 1:1 scale modeling facility enabled precise measurement of the RDS wash-off phenomenon under realistic condition considering two rainfall intensity scenarios (30 and 50 mm/h) and three RDS mass scenarios (100, 150 and 200 g/m²). (2) The RDS wash-off process was assessed in detail, investigating the behavior of six different sediment fractions during each simulated event in both suspended and dissolved forms. (3) The study entailed meticulous characterization of variables associated with RDS wash-off, generating a comprehensive dataset that included sediment loads and characteristics, rainfall intensity maps, surface elevations, runoff flows characterization and temporal evolution of total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS) and PSD during wash-off events.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Large-scale facility description

The large-scale physical modeling facility was comprised of a rainfall simulator and a 96 m² runoff channel (Fig. 1a). The rainfall simulator was engineered to allow for constant intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h. Rainfall was uniformly distributed over the facility surface (roadway) through a pressure-compensating irrigation drippers system, which incorporated a metallic mesh for breaking drops, achieve realistic uniformity and drop size (Naves et al., 2020b). The facility's runoff channel was divided into nine sub-catchments, five of which were of the street

type limited by the position of the gully pots and the surface slopes with no physical separation between them (B1, B2, B3, B4 and B5). The longitudinal and transversal slope were 2 % and 1 % according to typical drainage slopes found in real streets (Romero-Barreiro et al., 2015). The remaining four sub-catchments are of the roof type (B6, B7, B8 and B9) and drains runoff generated on the roofs directly to manholes (MHs) through gutters and downspout. The large-scale facility was equipped also with an underground pipe drainage system which consists of four MHs (N2, N3, N5 and N6) connected to the gully pots (GPs) and roofs, two non-connected to inlets MHs where it is possible to introduce additional pipe flows (N1 and N4), and an outlet pipe (O1), with a conduction direction starting at N1, N2, N3, N5, N6 and O1 (Fig. 1a). In this work, GP 1 and MH covers N2 and N3 were sealed to form a single catchment from sub-catchments B1 and B2 where the RDS was distributed attached to the curb along 2 m and draining all runoff to GP 2, which was connected to MH N3.

Five water level sensors (ultrasonic, UB500-18GM75-I-V15, Pepperl and Fuchs) were installed on the roadway (RW) to monitor water depths during hydraulic tests, and a triangular weir with an ultrasonic sensor (UB500-18GM75-I-V15, Pepperl and Fuchs) was fitted inside GP2 (lower section) to measure the generated runoff flow (Fig. 1b and c). Moreover, a video camera (Lumix GH4 camera) was set up to estimate the surface velocities distribution of runoff towards the GP 2 on the RW. In summary, the drainage system considered in this study consisted of three main components: RW (Fig. 1b), GP (Fig. 1c) and MH (Fig. 1d). The characteristics of each component are detailed in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Large-scale modeling facility used in this study. a) General detail map, b) roadway, water level sensors and video camera, c) gully pot and d) manhole.

Table 1
Characteristics of drainage system components in the large-scale modeling facility.

Component	Characteristic	Observation
Rainfall simulator	Rainfall intensities	30 and 50 mm/h
	Surface area	17.7 m ² (3 m × 5.9 m)
	Nozzle height	2.6 m above ground level
	Rainfall generator	One piped circuit with 2500 pressure-compensating irrigation drippers (PCJ-CNL, NetafimTM)
Roadway (RW)	Rainfall duration	10 min
	Type of pavement/material/texture	Rigid/concrete/ Smooth
	Manning's roughness coefficient	0.016
	Surface retention	1 mm
	Longitudinal/cross slope	1 %/2 %
	Porosity/preservation status	Compact and non-porous/no cracks and no erosion
	Drainage system	Without gutter/with gully pot/with curb (h = 0.06 m)
Gully pot (GP)	Type of material/surface geometry	Plastic/rectangular (b1 = 0.50, b2 = 0.20 m)
	Upper cross-section	Rectangular (b = 0.50, h = 0.18 m)
	Middle cross-section	Trapezoidal (b1 = 0.50, b2 = 0.18, h = 0.09 m)
	Lower cross-section, RDS collection area	Rectangular (b = 0.18, h = 0.14 m)
	Grate	Plastic, bar width/spacing: 0.02/0.02 m.
	Connection of GP and MH	4" plastic pipe with 0.30 m of length
Manhole (MH)	Type of material/surface geometry	Plastic/circular (diameter = 32")

2.2. RDS characterization

The RDS utilized in this study was collected from the RW of an urban tunnel in A Coruña, Spain, located on a 0.50 m wide strip next to the curb. Following this, a plastic fiber brush was employed to dislodge the RDS that was firmly adhered to the surface, referred to as the remaining RDS. This RDS was also gathered by dry vacuuming using a vacuum cleaner (Titan, 1400 W). The tunnel, which had a concrete RW, experienced an average daily traffic volume exceeding 15,000 vehicles per day. The collected RDS was subsequently sieved into six size fractions (< 63, 125, 250, 500, 1000 and 2000 µm) in accordance with the ISO 2591 method (ISO, 2007a). The sediment was then mixed to create a synthetic RDS that was representative of a real grain size, following reference studies: (García-Haba et al., 2023), (Naves et al., 2020), (Zafra et al., 2008), (Deletic and Orr, 2005), (Vaze and Chiew, 2002) and (Viklander, 1998). The synthetic RDS exhibited the following particle size distribution (PSD): < 63 = 9.90 %, < 125 = 23.6 %, < 250 = 41.6 %, < 500 = 66.8 %, < 1000 = 94.7 % and < 2000 µm = 100 %.

2.3. Hydraulic tests

Before the runoff wash-off tests were conducted, a hydraulic characterization of the physical modeling facility was completed. This characterization enabled precise measurement of runoff flow, which, when combined with comprehensive topographic data (Fig. 2a) and accurate intensity mapping (Fig. 2b), provided an essential foundation for the analysis of RDS transport processes. Two tests were conducted under the conditions utilized during the wash-off test considered in this study, with constant rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, each lasting for a duration of 10 min. The water depth at five points on the RW surface (Fig. 1b) and the runoff flow at the outlet of GP2 (Fig. 1c, lower section) were determined using ultrasonic sensors positioned on the surface and over a triangular weir (angle 60°) inside GP2, respectively. Calibration and signal processing, based on a moving median filter, were

detailed in Naves et al. (2020). Additional details on the rainfall intensity and elevation measurements for the entire facility are explained in Sañudo et al. (2024). Moreover, runoff velocities developed for both rainfall intensities considered were estimated around the RDS distribution area using Large Scale Particle Image Velocimetry from recorded videos of tailored experiments, employing the methodology developed and validated in (Naves et al., 2021), with fluorescent particles serving as tracers (Fig. 2c).

2.4. RDS wash-off tests

The RDS wash-off tests started with the distribution of a known RDS mass (synthetic RDS or initial RDS mass) over an area measuring 2 m in length and 1 m in width, situated adjacent to the road curb (Fig. 1a, RDS). To ensure a uniform distribution of the RDS on the RW, the deposition area was segmented into 18 quadrants, each measuring 0.17 m × 0.67 m. The RDS mass was then uniformly distributed across each quadrant using equipment composed of three horizontal sieves (height between sieves = 35 mm), with diameters of 6, 6 and 3 mm, respectively. This three-sieve equipment facilitated the random and uniform distribution of the RDS mass across the RW. Following the distribution of the RDS mass, the wash-off tests were conducted in accordance with the established experimental plan (Table 2). In this study, we then established six RDS wash-off scenarios, of which the L200_I30 and L100_I50 scenarios were those with the lowest and highest percentage potential for RDS wash-off by runoff, respectively. The scenario with the lowest RDS wash-off potential was characterized by high RDS mass and low rainfall intensity, and the scenario with the highest wash-off potential was characterized by low RDS mass and high rainfall intensity. The RDS wash-off potential was defined in this study from the percentage of mass remaining on the RW after each wash-off tests.

Upon the completion of each 10-min RDS wash-off test, the RDS collection methodology was based on three points from the large-scale facility drainage system: roadway RDS, gully pot RDS and manhole RDS. For the RDS of RW and GP, the remaining sediment mass in both components was collected using a wet vacuum (Nilfisk, Buddy II 18, water and dust vacuum, 1200 W) at the end of each test, lasting for 20 min. For the RDS of MH, it was collected from single samples inside the MH. These single samples of runoff were collected at established time intervals during the 10 min of each test: six bottles every 10 s (01:00), 13 bottles every 5 s (01:00–02:00), three bottles every 20 s (02:00–03:00), two bottles every 30 s (03:00–04:00) and seven bottles every minute (4:00–11:00). Resulting in 31 bottles for each test. This collection system enabled the analysis of runoff during the 10-min duration of each test and an additional minute, depending on the concentration time of the selected sub-basin in the large-scale modeling facility. The collection of runoff samples in the MH facilitated the determination of the pollutographs for each test (García et al., 2017; Li et al., 2023b). The water quality parameters considered included TS, TSS and TDS.

2.5. RDS wash-off analysis

Following each wash-off test, a mass balance was conducted in relation to the initially deposited RDS, the remaining RDS on the RW and inside the GP and that collected in the MH over the established time intervals (bottle system, see Section 2.4). The initial RDS mass corresponded to that established according to the considered test plan (Table 2). In calculating the remaining RDS mass after each wash-off test, the sum of the following variables was considered: remaining RDS on the RW (g), RDS collected in the GP (g) and RDS discharged in the MH (TS, in g). The RDS samples on the RW and in the GP were collected by wet vacuuming and dried at 105 °C for 24 h before their gravimetric and PSD analysis using laser diffraction (Beckman Coulter LS 13320, Aqueous Liquids Module, ISO 13320) (ISO, 2007b). During the PSD analysis, three replicates were run for each sample and 93 RDS size fractions between 0.375 and 2000 µm were considered. This range

Fig. 2. Spatial distributions for the topography (a), rainfall intensity (b) and flow velocities (c) associated with a rainfall intensity of 50 mm/h at the wash-off modeling facility.

of size fractions was transformed from the PSD established for the synthetic RDS (< 63, < 125, < 250, < 500, < 1000 and < 2000 μm).

All RDS samples on the RW and in the GP were PSD analyzed within a maximum period of seven days once the dry sample was obtained. The remaining RDS mass per size fraction on the RW and in the GP was calculated as the product between the percentage associated with each size fraction and the total mass of RDS collected by wet vacuuming. It should be noted that, although the PSD equipment provided results in volume percent, the conversion to mass percent was considered straightforward due to the minimal variability of density (0.6 %) in the RDS fractions analyzed (Naves et al., 2020). After each wash-off test, the percentage loss of RDS (error in the mass balance) was determined as the

difference between the masses of RDS initially deposited and the remaining on the RW, that collected in the GP, and that discharged inside the MH. The calculation of the latter will be detailed below.

The water samples collected from the MH were individually stored (in plastic bottles) according to the established collection time intervals (Section 2.4) and refrigerated at a temperature of 6 °C for the subsequent determination of TS (Standard Method 2540 B), TSS (Standard Method 2540 D), and TDS (Standard Method 2540C) (Bridgewater et al., 2012). All runoff water samples were analyzed within <48 h. Thus, 200 mL of runoff water was taken from each plastic bottle and deposited in a porcelain container for the determination of TS. This porcelain container was previously washed with 60 mL of distilled water, dried at 105 °C for

Table 2
Hydraulic and RDS wash-off tests considered.

Test	Scenario	Initial RDS mass (g/m ²)	Rainfall intensity (mm/h)	Water type	Duration (sec.)
T01	L0_I30	No RDS	30	Deionized	600
T02	L0_I50	No RDS	50	Deionized	600
T03	L100_I30	100	30	Deionized	600
T04	L100_I50 ^a	100	50	Deionized	600
T05	L150_I30	150	30	Deionized	600
T06	L150_I50	150	50	Deionized	600
T07	L200_I30 ^b	200	30	Deionized	600
T08	L200_I50	200	50	Deionized	600

^a Scenario of highest percentage potential for RDS wash-off.

^b Scenario of lowest percentage potential for RDS wash-off.

24 h and weighed on an analytical balance. After depositing the runoff water, the container was dried in an oven at 105 °C for 24 h. Lastly, TS concentration was determined gravimetrically. For the determination of the TSS concentration, the water samples from each plastic bottle were filtered (200 mL) using a sterile glass fiber filter of 47 mm in diameter and 0.45 µm pore size (MF-Millipore HAWP04700). Each glass fiber filter was previously washed with 60 mL of distilled water, dried at 105 °C for 24 h, and weighed on an analytical balance. After filtration, the filters were dried at a constant temperature of 105 °C and for 24 h. Lastly, TSS concentration was determined gravimetrically. The difference between TS and TSS allowed the calculation of the TDS concentration in the water samples from each bottle (Bridgewater et al., 2012).

The direct analysis of RDS (TS, TSS and TDS) in the water samples collected from the MH was conducted for 8 main bottles, which were selected based on their representativeness over time in the pollutograph (García et al., 2017; Li et al., 2023b) generated for turbidity (TUR) and electrical conductivity (EC). TUR (Standard Method 2130 B) and EC (Standard Method 2510 B) (Bridgewater et al., 2012) were measured in each of the 31 bottles generated in each RDS wash-off test. The concentrations of TS, TSS and TDS for the remaining 23 water bottles were calculated from linear regression models (Xue et al., 2020) between TUR – TSS ($R^2 > 0.980$) and EC – TDS ($R^2 > 0.900$). This was based on the report of very strong correlations between TUR – TSS (Bright and Mager, 2020; Li et al., 2024) and EC – TDS (Rusydi, 2018; Taylor et al., 2018). Nevertheless, for the totally of the RDS wash-off tests, not all of the 23 bottles were further analyzed for TS regression calculus as the volume recollected (mL) in the first bottles were inexistent because of the null development of flow in the first instants of time of the wash-off test, or the bottle did not have enough volume (mL) for TUR and EC analysis; and, in correspondence, PSD analysis (Winston et al., 2023).

The PSD for each sample was measured using laser diffraction (Beckman Coulter LS 13320, Aqueous Liquids Module, ISO 13320) (ISO, 2007b). We performed three repetitions for each sample and considered 93 RDS size fractions between 0.375 and 2000 µm. This range of size fractions was transformed from the PSD established for the synthetic RDS (< 63, < 125, < 250, < 500, < 1000 and < 2000 µm). The mass of RDS per size fraction in the water samples within the MH was calculated as the product between the percentage associated with each size fraction and the total mass collected in the MH (García-Haba et al., 2023). Finally, all the information collected in this work (dataset) can be consulted in the following open access repository: <https://zenodo.org/record/13828933>.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The normality of data series for each study variable was assessed using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (p -value > 0.05) (Toranjian and Marofi, 2017). Subsequently, we conducted an analysis of potential relationships between the considered variables through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Pearson correlation (Shajib et al., 2019).

The PCA involved three steps (Greenacre et al., 2022): (1) standardizing measurements to ensure equal weight in the analysis by automatically scaling the data to create new variables with a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. (2) Calculating the covariance matrix by identifying eigenvalues and their corresponding eigenvectors. (3) Eliminating components that explained only a small proportion of variation in the datasets. We retained only principal components with eigenvalues greater than one for further analysis. Lastly, the retained principal components were not subjected to any rotation. All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics V.19 with a confidence interval of 95 %.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hydraulic characterization

The results of the hydraulic characterization of the large-scale modeling facility revealed stationary runoff flows of up to 0.11 and 0.24 L/s (GP outlet) for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively (Fig. 1S). A delay in the runoff hydrograph of 38 and 77 s, respectively, was also observed in relation to the start of the RDS wash-off test (total duration = 10 min). This delay in runoff flows was possibly related to the concentration time and the initial rainfall retention of the sub-basin considered (Al-Mamun et al., 2023). The findings showed maximum flow depths around 1.0 mm and between 4.0 and 6.0 mm at 0.75 m and next to the curb of the RW, respectively (Fig. 2b). Moreover, the results showed flow velocities of up to 0.18 and 0.20 m/s for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively. The maximum runoff flow velocities were observed near the GP (Fig. 2c). Two dominant directions were also visualized in the runoff flow towards the GP. A first runoff flow in a transverse direction to the curb of the RW, with water depths around 1.0 mm, and a second runoff flow attached to the curb of the RW, which collected the previous flow and drained it towards the GP (flow depth between 3 and 6 mm).

3.2. Distribution of RDS wash-off

The results showed that as the rainfall intensity increased, the remaining RDS mass on the RW at the end of each wash-off test tended to decrease (Fig. 3). An increase of 66.7 % in rainfall intensity (from 30 to 50 mm/h) generated a decrease in the remaining RDS mass of 37.5 %, 33.9 % and 31.1 % for the initial RDS mass scenarios of 100, 150 and 200 g/m², respectively. Increased initial RDS mass led to a decrease in the effect of rainfall intensity on RDS wash-off from RW, increasing remaining RDS mass after wash-off. This direct relationship between the initial RDS mass and the remaining RDS mass was analyzed through the development of linear regression models for rainfall intensities of 30 mm/h ($R^2 = 0.999$) and 50 mm/h ($R^2 = 0.997$) (Fig. 4a). Studies identified that the presence of a high initial mass of RDSs in the runoff could lead to an increase in the percentage of RDS mass remaining on the RW at the end of the simulated events (Hong et al., 2016). This phenomenon was attributed to a decrease in the kinetic energy of the RDS during the formation of the runoff, which in turn was related to the formation of crusts or accumulation sites of RDS on the RW (Russell et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2023).

Additionally, the results suggested through the developed regression models, that with the decrease in initial RDS mass, the remaining RDS mass on the RW at the end of the wash-off tests could tend to zero. That is, for this scenario to occur regarding the remaining RDS mass, the initial RDS masses on the RW had to be low, at 30 and 68 g/m² for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively (Fig. 4a). Indeed, these scenarios were likely to be of low initial RDS mass, contrary to the high initial RDS mass scenarios (100–200 g/m²) simulated in this study using the wash-off modeling facility. Under the high initial RDS mass scenarios simulated in this study, there was always remaining RDS mass on the RW at the end of the wash-off tests (Fig. 3). These findings also

Fig. 3. Masses of remaining RDS on the RW, collected in the GP and discharged into the MH after each wash-off test. Simulated initial RDS mass scenarios on the RW (L): 100, 150 and 200 g/m². Simulated rainfall intensity scenarios (I): 30 and 50 mm/h.

Fig. 4. Linear regression models between the masses of RDS remaining on RW (a), RDS collected by the GP (b) and RDS discharged within the MH (c), and the initial RDS mass (100, 150 and 200 g/m²).

hinted at the existence of a maximum limit to be able to wash-off the entirety of the RDS initially deposited on the RW, according to the rainfall intensities and the particular conditions of the simulated drainage system. In each particular case, the results also hinted at the need to forecast this maximum limit of initial RDS mass to wash-off in order to achieve greater efficiency in street sweeping operations (RDS removal) in urban environments. Studies reported that under scenarios of high initial RDS mass it was likely that there was a limitation to develop a turbulent flow state in the runoff, which resulted in an incomplete wash-off of the entire mass of RDS, regardless of the rainfall intensity (Egodawatta et al., 2007).

Contrary to the RW, the findings showed that as the rainfall intensity increased, the collected RDS mass in the GP tended to increase at the end of each wash-off test (Fig. 3). An increase of 66.7 % in rainfall intensity generated an increase in the collected RDS mass in the GP of 36.2 %, 23.6 % and 24.1 % for the initial RDS mass scenarios of 100, 150 and 200 g/m², respectively. As initial RDS mass increased, the effect of rainfall intensity on GP-collected mass decreased, resulting in less mass deposited (removed) after the simulated rainfall event. This inverse relationship between the initial RDS mass and the collected RDS mass in the GP was analyzed through the development of linear regression models for rainfall intensities of 30 mm/h ($R^2 = 0.946$) and 50 mm/h ($R^2 = 0.973$) (Fig. 4b). The findings suggested through the developed models that after each wash-off test there tended to be a minimum RDS mass inside the GP around 16 and 38 g/m² for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively. The results hinted that the GP might have been able to collect (removal) the entirety of these initial RDS masses coming from the RW, according to the simulated rainfall intensities. Research reported that the RDS accumulation process in the GP was initially dominated by sedimentation. When a substantial bed of RDS was created, the bed began to interact with the runoff flow, the sediment removal efficiency decreased, and the bed eventually reached a mass balance (Rietveld et al., 2020). The results also hinted that the RDS accumulation within the GP decreased the particle retention efficiency, which led to an increase in the transport of RDSs to the drainage systems located downstream (MHs and sewer pipes). Lastly, the findings suggested that this wash-off modeling facility could be used to simulate the maximum RDS removal capacity for different types of GPs according to various rainfall intensities, initial RDS masses and GP design geometric characteristics.

The results showed that as the rainfall intensity increased, the RDS mass discharged in the MH (TSS + TDS) during the wash-off tests tended to increase (Fig. 3). An increase of 66.7 % in the rainfall intensity generated an increase in the RDS mass discharged in the MH of 4.64 %, 8.75 % and 5.72 % for the initial RDS mass scenarios of 100, 150 and 200 g/m², respectively. With increased initial RDS mass, the effect of rainfall intensity on MH-discharged mass increased, leading to more mass discharged after wash-off. This direct relationship between the

initial RDS mass and the percentage of the initial RDS mass discharged in the MH was analyzed by developing linear regression models for rainfall intensities of 30 mm/h ($R^2 = 0.958$) and 50 mm/h ($R^2 = 0.895$) (Fig. 4c). The findings suggested through the developed models, that with the reduction of the initial RDS mass from the RW, the mass discharged in the MH tended to a minimum limit value (2.15 and 2.61 g/m², respectively). The results hinted that under the scenarios of high RDS mass simulated on the RW, the RDS mass discharged in the MH possibly did not tend to be zero in a short time interval. Indeed, the RDS wash-off possibly depended on the concentration time of the large-scale modeling facility used and the monitoring time considered (10 min). Furthermore, the possible contribution of RDSs from the bed of the GP (RDS collection area, Table 1) should be considered when the RDS of the RW tended to be depleted.

The findings suggested that the behavior of the RDS on the RW, GP and MH was interconnected. The RW possibly acted as the initial source where the RDS was affected by the rainfall; here, the intense rainfall and the high initial RDS mass determined how much RDS was removed and transported to the next component of the drainage system. Under the simulated scenarios of lowest (L200_I30) and highest potential (L100_I50) in terms of percentage of RDS washed-off (Fig. 3), it was observed that the remaining RDS masses on the RW were 67.1 % and 18.2 %, respectively. The GP, being the next in the sequence of the drainage system, received the RDS washed-off from the RW. The mass of RDS collected in the GP not only depended on the mass transported from the RW but also on its own collection capacity, which could be affected by sedimentation and the formation of a bed of RDS that interacted with the runoff inflow. Under the simulated scenarios of lowest and highest potential of RDS wash-off, it was observed that the RDS masses collected in the GP were 21.7 % and 65.5 %, respectively. The MH received the RDS that was transported through the RW and that was not removed by the GP. The RDS mass discharged in the MH reflected the efficiency of the complete system in handling the wash-off of the RDS under different conditions of intense rainfall and high initial RDS masses. Under the simulated scenarios of lowest and highest potential of RDS wash-off, it was observed that the RDS masses discharged in the MH were 4.74 % and 6.81 %, respectively. Indeed, the intense rainfall and the high initial RDS mass were key factors that affected this transport at each component of the road drainage system. Lastly, in relation to the errors of the RDS mass balance executed after each wash-off test, the results evidenced a variation between 5.37 and 10.4 % (RDS loss) with respect to the initial RDS mass deposited on the RW.

3.3. RDS particle size distribution

3.3.1. Roadway

The findings showed that as the rainfall intensity increased (66.7 %), the PSD of the remaining RDS on the RW tended to be coarser at the end of wash-off tests. For example, it was observed that the D_{10} of the RDS for the L100_I30 and L100_I50 scenarios were 103 μm and 114 μm , respectively. The results also suggested that the previous trend was similar when the initial RDS mass on the RW increased (Fig. 5). This study paid special attention to the finest RDS fraction (D_{10}), as this size fraction has been reported as the one that associated the highest concentrations of pollutants in road environments (e.g., heavy metals and hydrocarbons) (Lanzerstorfer, 2018; Loganathan et al., 2013).

When performing a RDS wash-off analysis from the six size fractions considered, a differentiated behavior was observed on the RW with reference to the size fraction of 250 μm . The size fraction between 125 and 250 μm was the one that tended to show the highest remaining RDS mass on the RW after each wash-off test (Fig. 6). The results suggested a decreasing trend in the remaining RDS mass for size fractions <250 μm (finest RDS fraction). For example, under the L100_I50 scenario (highest wash-off potential scenario), the percentage masses remaining on the RW for the size fractions between 125 and 250 μm , 63–125 μm and < 63 μm were 26.3 %, 20.1 % and 10.0 %, respectively. Namely, the road runoff washed-off 73.7 %, 79.9 % and 90.0 % of the RDS from the RW, respectively. The results also hinted that the percentage of remaining mass of the finest RDS fraction (< 250 μm) tended to increase as the

Fig. 6. Percent mass of RDS in each component of the drainage system after the simulated wash-off scenarios. Analysis by size fraction, rainfall intensity and initial RDS mass on the RW.

Fig. 5. D_{10} , D_{50} and D_{90} for RDS after simulated wash-off scenarios. Analysis by rainfall intensity and initial RDS mass on the RW.

initial RDS mass increased. The previous trend was analyzed by developing linear regression models for rainfall intensities of 30 mm/h ($R^2 > 0.833$) and 50 mm/h ($R^2 > 0.876$). This trend was more evident with the increase in rainfall intensity (50 mm/h; Fig. 7a). On average, the results hinted at an increase of 11.8 % and 11.4 % in the remaining RDS mass ($< 250 \mu\text{m}$) for each increase of 100 g/m^2 in the initial RDS mass, for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively.

3.3.2. Gully pot

The results showed that as the rainfall intensity increased (66.7 %), the PSD of the collected RDS tended to be coarser at the end of the wash-off tests. For instance, it was observed that the D_{10} of the RDS for the L100_I30 and L100_I50 scenarios were $106 \mu\text{m}$ and $128 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The results also suggested that the previous trend in the GP was similar when the initial RDS mass on the RW increased (Fig. 5). Studies reported that intense rainfall generated a shorter residence time of runoff in the GP, which limited the sedimentation of fine particles and favored the transport of coarser particles towards the MH (Schiff et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2019).

The findings suggested a decreasing trend in the RDS mass collected in the GP for size fractions $< 250 \mu\text{m}$ (finest RDS fraction). For example, under the L100_I50 scenario (highest wash-off potential), the percentage masses collected in the GP for size fractions between 125 and $250 \mu\text{m}$, 63 – $125 \mu\text{m}$ and $< 63 \mu\text{m}$ were 65.3 %, 51.7 % and 31.4 %, respectively.

Fig. 7. Linear regression models for the finest RDS fractions ($< 250 \mu\text{m}$) and a rainfall intensity of 50 mm/h. Relationship between the masses of RDS remaining on RW (a), RDS collected in GP (b) and RDS discharged within MH (c), and the initial RDS mass (100 , 150 and 200 g/m^2).

This decreasing trend in the collected mass of the finer RDS fraction was similar for all simulated scenarios (Fig. 6), although it was more evident as the rainfall intensity increased (50 mm/h). Moreover, the findings suggested that the percentage of mass of the finer RDS fraction collected by the GP tended to decrease as the initial RDS mass on the RW increased. The previous trend was analyzed through the development of linear regression models for rainfall intensities of 30 mm/h ($R^2 > 0.349$) and 50 mm/h ($R^2 > 0.906$). This trend was more evident with the increase in rainfall intensity (50 mm/h; Fig. 7b). On average, the results suggested a decrease of 2.87 % and 13.9 % in the percentage of mass collected (RDS removed) by the GP for each increase of 100 g/m^2 in the initial RDS mass on the RW, for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively. Studies reported that GPs could have limited efficacy in capturing fine particles during intense rainfall events. This was due to the high speed and volume of runoff potentially allowing fine particles to be transported to the MH without being captured by the GP (Muthanna and Viklander, 2019).

3.3.3. Manhole

The results showed that as the rainfall intensity increased (66.7 %), the PSD of the discharged RDS tended to be coarser at the end of the wash-off tests. For instance, it was observed that the D_{10} of the RDS discharged in the MH for the L100_I30 and L100_I50 scenarios were $24 \mu\text{m}$ and $29 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The results also suggested that the previous trend in the MH was similar when the initial RDS mass on the RW increased (Fig. 5). Studies reported that as the rainfall intensity increased, the flow rate of water on the RWs and in the drainage system could also increase. This higher velocity could transport larger and heavier RDSs towards the MHs and sewer pipes (Malek Mohammadi et al., 2020). Moreover, research reported that high runoff volumes could re-suspend the RDSs previously deposited in the drainage system, including the coarser particles deposited in the GP (Wijesiri et al., 2016). This re-suspension phenomenon possibly generated a reactivation of the RDS wash-off, causing the coarse RDS fraction to be transported from the GP to the MH.

The findings suggested an increasing trend in the RDS mass discharged in the MH for size fractions $< 250 \mu\text{m}$ (finest RDS fraction). For example, under the L100_I50 scenario (highest wash-off potential), the percentage masses discharged in the MH for size fractions between 125 and $250 \mu\text{m}$, 63 – $125 \mu\text{m}$ and $< 63 \mu\text{m}$ were 8.36 %, 28.2 % and 58.6 %, respectively. This increasing trend in the mass discharged of the finer RDS fraction was similar for all simulated scenarios (Fig. 6), although it was more evident as the rainfall intensity increased (50 mm/h). The findings also suggested that the percentage of mass of the finer RDS fraction discharged within the MH tended to increase slightly as the initial RDS mass on the RW increased. The previous trend was analyzed through the development of linear regression models for rainfall intensities of 30 mm/h ($R^2 > 0.813$) and 50 mm/h ($R^2 > 0.905$). This trend was more evident with the increase in rainfall intensity (50 mm/h; Fig. 7c). The results comparatively showed differences between the scenarios of lowest (L200_I30) and highest (L100_I50) potential of RDS wash-off. During the scenario of highest wash-off potential, a higher discharge of fine size RDS in the MH was observed (125 – $250 \mu\text{m} = +4.70 \%$, 63 – $125 \mu\text{m} = +15.6 \%$ and $< 63 \mu\text{m} = +23.2 \%$) compared to the scenario of lowest wash-off potential. The results suggested that as the RDS mass on the RW increased, the percentage of mass discharged in the MH of the finer RDS fraction tended to increase. Studies reported that a larger amount of RDS on the RW surface increased the probability that it would be re-suspended and transported by the runoff to the drainage system, including the finer RDS particles (Kayhanian et al., 2012; Winston et al., 2023).

3.4. RDS transport in the drainage system

Regarding the behavior of the sediment PSD in the three components of the simulated drainage system, the results suggested that as the

rainfall intensity increased, the PSD tended to be coarser in each component after each wash-off test. This trend was observed both in the RDS remaining on the RW, the RDS collected by the GP, and the RDS discharged in the MH, and was consistent regardless of the initial RDS mass distributed on the RW (Fig. 5). These findings also suggested a greater transport of the finer RDS fraction (D_{10}) after each wash-off test. Hence, the intense rainfall played a relevant role in the sediment transport and PSD in the drainage system, which possibly had significant implications in the design and management of these systems. In order of importance, the greatest D_{10} variations of the RDS masses obtained at the end of the tests with the increase of the rainfall intensity were observed in the GP (22–50 μm), RW (3–10 μm) and MH (3–9 μm), respectively. The D_{10} in the GP for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h were 106 μm and 128 μm , respectively. This trend suggested that the collection or capture efficiency of the finer RDS fraction by the GP did not increase considerably with the increase of the rainfall intensity. Namely, it was suggested that the mass of the finer RDS fraction discharged in the MH tended to increase with the increase in rainfall intensity. The results also suggested that the GP simulated in this study mainly removed the coarser RDS fraction (Fig. 8) and that its removal efficiency increased with rainfall intensity. On average, for size fraction $>250 \mu\text{m}$, GP removed 20.6 % and 44.9 % of the RDS mass for rainfall intensities of 30 and 50 mm/h, respectively (Fig. 6).

Additionally, we simulated wash-off scenarios under high initial RDS masses on the RW (100–200 g/m^2). These scenarios could generate an early overload of the GP (limited capacity), which could decrease its efficiency in the capture of the finer RDSs throughout each of the simulated wash-off tests. The D_{10} variations of the RDS on the RW (3–10 μm), also suggested that there was part of the finer RDS fraction that was not washed-off by the runoff during the simulations. Studies reported the following limiting phenomena of the wash-off of the finer RDS accumulated on the RWs (Aryal et al., 2005; Grimm et al., 2024; Hong et al., 2016; Shi et al., 2017; Verbanck et al., 1994; Zhao et al., 2018, 2022): development of a protective RDS crust (agglutination of fine particles), saturation of the drainage system with RDS (limited capacity of the GP), modification of the hydraulic flow on the RW surface

(diversion of the runoff flow), the characteristics of the RDS itself (finer and cohesive sediment) and the characteristics of the RW surface (rough texture that retains fine particles). The average PSD of sediment, from the finest to the coarsest, in the components of the simulated drainage system was as follows: MH $>$ GP $>$ RW (Fig. 8). This sequence in relation to the finest and most polluting fraction of the RDS suggested an order of importance for intervening in the different components of the simulated road drainage system. For example, through the implementation of RDS traps and regular sweeping in the RWs, and the implementation of advanced filtration systems in the GPs and MHs, which significantly reduced the pollutant load. The simulations in the wash-off modeling facility likely highlighted the need to implement specific strategies in each system component to manage fine RDS pollution during wash-off events. Under the highest wash-off potential scenario (L100_I50) and for the $<63 \mu\text{m}$ size fraction of RDS, the results indicated that 59.2 % was discharged in the MH, 9.6 % remained on the RW, and 31.2 % was collected in the GP.

In relation to the general behavior of the finer RDS fraction ($< 250 \mu\text{m}$) in the three components of the simulated system, the results suggested that this size fraction tended to be more susceptible to be washed-off, especially under conditions of low initial RDS mass and high rainfall intensity (L100_I50 scenario). However, as the initial RDS mass increased (from 100 to 200 g/m^2), the percentage of mass of this fine fraction that remained on the RW at the end of the wash-off test tended to increase, while that collected by the GP decreased (L200_I50 scenario; Fig. 6). This suggested that the GP could have limited efficacy to capture fine particles during intense rainfall events. Instead, the percentage of fine size RDS discharged in the MH tended to increase with the rainfall intensity and the initial RDS mass on the RW (L100_I50 scenario). This suggested that a greater mass of RDS on the RW surface might have increased the probability that the finer particles would be re-suspended and transported by the runoff to the MH Mitchell et al. (2019) and Zhao et al. (2018) reported similar results. Under the scenario of highest potential of RDS wash-off (L100_I50), the results showed on average for the size fraction $<250 \mu\text{m}$ that the runoff washed-off 81.7 % of the RDS mass initially deposited on the RW. Of this washed-off size fraction, 49.6 %

Fig. 8. PSD comparison of the RDS in each component of the drainage system. Initial RDS mass on the RW, RDS remaining on the RW, RDS collected in the GP and RDS discharged in the MH.

was captured by the GP and 32.1 % was discharged in the MH. For the size fraction $<63 \mu\text{m}$, the percentages associated with each component of the drainage system were as follows: 90.4 % (RW), 31.2 % (GP) and 59.2 % (MH).

Regarding the coarse RDS fraction (250–1000 μm), the results demonstrated that it tended to be less susceptible to wash-off, especially under conditions of high initial RDS mass and low rainfall intensity (L200_I30 scenario). As the initial RDS mass increased (from 100 to 200 g/m^2), the percentage of this coarse fraction that remained on the RW after the wash-off tests tended to increase, while the mass collected by the GP decreased (Fig. 6). This suggested that the GP could also have limited efficacy to capture coarse particles during intense rainfall events. Instead, the percentage of coarse size RDS discharged in the MH tended to decrease as a low rainfall intensity and high initial RDS mass on the RW increased (L200_I30 scenario). This suggested that a greater RDS mass on the RW surface might have decreased the probability that the coarser particles would be re-suspended and transported by the runoff to the MH. Under the scenario of highest potential of RDS wash-off (L100_I50), the results showed on average for the size fraction between 250 and 1000 μm that the runoff washed-off 80.3 % of the mass initially deposited on the RW. Of this washed-off size fraction, 75.3 % was captured by the GP and 5 % was discharged in the MH. For the size fraction between 1000 and 2000 μm , the percentages associated with each component of the drainage system were as follows: 72.5 % (RW), 69.2 % (GP) and 3.3 % (MH).

3.5. Key variables in RDS transport

The results showed through a PCA the existence of two main components, which explained 95.6 % (total variance) of the behavior of all the variables considered during the wash-off tests (determinant <0.001). The variables considered were the following: initial RDS mass

on the RW, rainfall intensity and RDS masses by size fraction in each of the components of the drainage system after the wash-off tests. In order of importance, the following variables were associated with the first component (total variance: 58.4 %): GP-500 μm > GP-1000 μm > MH-125 μm > MH-250 μm > MH-500 μm > MH-1000 μm > GP-250 μm > MH-2000 μm > MH-63 μm > GP-125 μm > rain intensity > GP-2000 μm > GP-63 μm (Fig. 9). In order of importance, the following variables were associated with the second component (total variance: 35.9 %): RW-250 μm > RW-500 μm > RW-125 μm > RW-2000 μm > RW-1000 μm > RW-63 μm > initial RDS mass. The results suggested that the RDS collected in the GP and discharged in the MH was more influenced by the rainfall intensity than by the initial RDS mass deposited on the RW. Conversely, the findings suggested that the RDS remaining on the RW after the wash-off tests was more influenced by the initial RDS mass deposited than by the rainfall intensity.

The results suggested that the management of the RW sediment should be more focused on the control of the initial RDS mass accumulated on the surface. This management of the RW sediment should probably be more focused on cleaning activities for its removal (e.g., mechanical sweeping, vacuuming and pressure washing). Instead, the findings suggested that the management of the RDS collected by the GP and discharged in the MH should be more focused on the rainfall intensity. The rainfall intensity appeared to be one of the key variables to be considered in the study of the collection or capture of the RDS by GPs and the discharge of the RDS in MHs. In other words, the findings suggested that the design of street cleaning systems should have primarily focused on removing the RDS mass accumulated during dry periods on the RW (coarse and fine fractions). The findings also suggested that the design of RDS capture systems in GPs and MHs should have primarily focused on the effect of rainfall intensity on the transport of coarse and fine RDS fractions during wash-off events, respectively. Indeed, the initial RDS mass and the rainfall intensity were, together, fundamental

Fig. 9. PCA plot for rainfall intensity, initial RDS mass on the RW, and the masses of RDS remaining on the RW, collected by the GP and discharged to the MH by size fraction after the wash-off tests.

for the interpretation of the behavior of the RDS in the three simulated components. Studies also recognized the rainfall intensity and the accumulated RDS mass on the RWs as some of the key variables in the design of the components of the drainage systems (Allen et al., 2017).

The findings indicated through a Pearson correlation analysis, the existence of significant relationships of considerable to very strong between the components of the drainage system of the modeling facility. The variables considered for this analysis were the mass percentages of RDS by size fraction in each of the components after the simulated wash-off scenarios (Table S1). The results showed for the finer RDS fraction (< 250 μm), that the size fraction <63 μm was the one that associated the best linear correlation coefficients (83.3 % of the r-Pearson ≥ 0.80) between the components of the drainage system. The results suggested this size fraction as an indicator to study the behavior of the finer RDS in the drainage system during the wash-off phenomenon. Studies also reported this size fraction as the most suitable to study the transport of the finer RDS and the pollution associated with it during the wash-off events by runoff (Jeong et al., 2020). In relation to the coarse RDS fraction (250–1000 μm), the results suggested that the size fraction between 500 and 1000 μm was the most suitable (83.3 % of the r-Pearson ≥ 0.80) to study its transport by runoff. In addition, the results suggested a significant inverse relationship between the remaining RDS mass on the RW and that collected by the GP (r-Pearson between -0.553 and -0.999), and between the remaining RDS mass on the RW and that discharged in the MH (r-Pearson between -0.718 and -0.956) at the end of the wash-off tests. In this study, the correlation between the remaining RDS mass on the RW and that discharged in the MH was better compared to the correlation between the remaining RDS mass on the RW and that collected by the GP during the wash-off simulations. This trend in Pearson correlations possibly suggested that the GP should have been optimized in its design to increase the effectiveness in capturing fine RDS transported from the RW during simulated wash-off events.

4. Conclusions

The results on RDS wash-off in road drainage systems under intense rainfall and high RDS masses, using a unique large-scale modeling facility, allow us to visualize the following conclusions.

The results suggest a clear hierarchy regarding the wash-off of fine RDSs in the different components of the drainage system. The MH is the critical component, receiving the largest mass of fine RDS (< 63 μm : 59.2 %). The findings suggest the following intervention sequence in the different components of the drainage system for controlling pollution associated with fine RDS: MH (59.2 %) > GP (31.2 %) > RW (9.6 %). Furthermore, the results indicate the existence of maximum limits (30–68 g/m^2) for the complete wash-off of the initial RDS mass on the RW during the simulated intense rainfall events (30–50 mm/h). Since street sweeping is a pollution control strategy, the findings imply the need to forecast these maximum limits to achieve higher efficiencies and reduce the RDS masses discharged into the MHs. Indeed, GPs also play a fundamental role in wash-off RDS from the RW to the MH. In each particular case, the results suggest the need to forecast the minimum RDS collection capacity within the GP (16–38 g/m^2) to evaluate its contribution to the removal of washed RDS from the RWs. When there are high RDS masses on the RW and short-duration intense rainfalls, the findings also suggest that at the end of the rainfall event, there is still a minimal RDS discharge (2.15–2.61 g/m^2) from the RW and GP to the MH.

The results suggest that the design of street cleaning systems (e.g., RDS traps and sweeping equipment) should focus on removing the coarser fraction (250–1000 μm) rather than the finer fraction (< 250 μm) of the remaining RDS on the RW after wash-off events. During the highest potential wash-off scenario (L100_I50), the findings indicate that 80.3 % of the coarser RDS fraction (250–1000 μm) is transported to the GP (75.3 %) and MH (5 %). The findings also suggest that for the

design and operation of these street cleaning systems, the RDS mass accumulated during dry periods is more relevant than the rainfall intensity. Instead, the results suggest that the design of RDS capture systems in GPs (e.g., capture grates and baskets) and MHs (e.g., internal sedimentation devices and geotextile filters) during wash-off events should focus on the coarser and finer RDS fractions, respectively. During the highest potential wash-off scenario (L100_I50), the findings indicate that 81.7 % of the finer RDS fraction (< 250 μm) is transported to the GP (49.6 %) and MH (32.1 %). Lastly, the results suggest that the size fractions <63 μm and between 500 and 1000 μm are representative of the finest and coarsest RDS fractions during wash-off in the studied drainage system.

However, it is important to consider the following limitations detected in this research: 1) the interaction between the study variables is possibly more complex and non-linear. 2) The efficiency of RDS wash-off also depends on the characteristics of the drainage system, such as the slope of the RW, the capacity of the GP and the design of the MH. Lastly, for future research, the following aspects are recommended: 1) Evaluate the influence of other factors such as pavement type (concrete and asphalt), RDS physicochemical composition and runoff water quality (mixture of RDS and deionized water). 2) Implement strategies for monitoring and controlling water quality at different components in the drainage system to deepen the study of the phenomenon of RDS wash-off by road runoff.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

C.A. Zafra-Mejía: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **D. Hernández-Medina:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J. Suárez:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **J. Naves:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **J. Anta:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.178195>.

Data availability

The authors declare that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper and its Supplementary Information files. Should any raw data files be needed in another format they are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. Source data are provided with this paper.

References

- Addison-Atkinson, W., Chen, A.S., Memon, F.A., Anta, J., Naves, J., Cea, L., 2024. Investigation of uniform and graded sediment wash-off in an urban drainage system: numerical model validation from a rainfall simulator in an experimental facility. *J. Hydrol.* 629, 130561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.130561>.
- Al Ali, S., Bonhomme, C., Dubois, P., Chebbo, G., 2017. Investigation of the wash-off process using an innovative portable rainfall simulator allowing continuous monitoring of flow and turbidity at the urban surface outlet. *Sci. Total Environ.* 609, 17–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.07.106>.
- Allen, D., Arthur, S., Haynes, H., Olive, V., 2017. Multiple rainfall event pollution transport by sustainable drainage systems: the fate of fine sediment pollution. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 14, 639–652. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-016-1177-y>.
- Al-Mamun, A., Ibrahim, S.L.B., Masbah, D.I., Daud, J.I., Khan, N.K.E.M.Y., 2023. Calculation of proper time of concentration for drainage design in construction projects for urban development. *Construction* 3, 190–195. <https://doi.org/10.15282/construction.v3i2.9664>.
- Aryal, R.K., Jinadasa, H.K.P.K., Furumai, H., Nakajima, F., 2005. A long-term suspended solids runoff simulation in a highway drainage system. *Water Sci. Technol.* 52, 159–167.
- Bridgewater, L., Association, A.P.H., Association, A.W.W., Federation, W.E., 2012. *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*. American Public Health Association.
- Bright, C.E., Mager, S.M., 2020. Contribution of particulate organic matter to riverine suspended material in the Glendhu experimental catchments, Otago, New Zealand. *J. Hydrol. N. Z.* 55, 89–105. <https://doi.org/10.3316/informit.854357441890922>.
- Chen, T., Shu, J., Han, L., Tian, G., Yang, G., Lv, J., 2022. Modeling the effects of topography and slope gradient of an artificially formed slope on runoff, sediment yield, water and soil loss of sandy soil. *CATENA* 212, 106060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106060>.
- Deletic, A., Orr, D.W., 2005. Pollution buildup on road surfaces. *J. Environ. Eng.* 131, 49–59. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9372\(2005\)131:1\(49\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9372(2005)131:1(49)).
- Egodawatta, P., Thomas, E., Goonetilleke, A., 2007. Mathematical interpretation of pollutant wash-off from urban road surfaces using simulated rainfall. *Water Res.* 41, 3025–3031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.03.037>.
- Faisal, M., Wu, Z., Wang, H., Lin, X., Hussain, Z., Azam, M.I., 2022. Potential heavy metals pollution contribution from wash-off of urban road-dust. *Toxics* 10, 397. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics10070397>.
- Ferreira, C.S.S., Walsh, R.P.D., Ferreira, A.J.D., 2018. Degradation in urban areas. *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health, Sustainable soil management and land restoration* 5, 19–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2018.04.001>.
- García, J.T., Espín-Leal, P., Viguera-Rodríguez, A., Castillo, L.G., Carrillo, J.M., Martínez-Solano, P.D., Nevado-Santos, S., 2017. Urban runoff characteristics in combined sewer overflows (CSOs): analysis of storm events in southeastern Spain. *Water* 9, 303. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w9050303>.
- García-Haba, E., Naves, J., Hernández-Crespo, C., Goya-Heredia, A., Suárez, J., Anta, J., Andrés-Doménech, L., 2023. Influence of sediment characteristics on long-term hydrology and water quality behaviour during the clogging process of a permeable asphalt. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 53, 103658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2023.103658>.
- Ghosh, S.P., Maiti, S.K., 2018. Evaluation of heavy metal contamination in roadside deposited sediments and road surface runoff: a case study. *Environ. Earth Sci.* 77, 267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-018-7370-1>.
- Gorgoglione, A., Bombardelli, F.A., Pitton, B.J.L., Oki, L.R., Haver, D.L., Young, T.M., 2019. Uncertainty in the parameterization of sediment build-up and wash-off processes in the simulation of sediment transport in urban areas. *Environ. Model. Software* 111, 170–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.09.022>.
- Greenacre, M., Groenen, P.J.F., Hastie, T., D'Enza, A.L., Markos, A., Tuzhilina, E., 2022. Principal component analysis. *Nat. Rev. Methods Primers* 2, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00184-w>.
- Grimm, A.G., Tirpak, R.A., Winston, R.J., 2024. Monitoring the impacts of rainfall characteristics on sediment loss from road construction sites. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 31, 32428–32440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-33361-3>.
- Haynes, H.M., Taylor, K.G., Rothwell, J., Byrne, P., 2020. Characterisation of road-dust sediment in urban systems: a review of a global challenge. *J. Soil. Sediment.* 20, 4194–4217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-020-02804-y>.
- Hong, Y., Bonhomme, C., Le, M.-H., Chebbo, G., 2016. A new approach of monitoring and physically-based modelling to investigate urban wash-off process on a road catchment near Paris. *Water Res.* 102, 96–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.06.027>.
- Hu, L., Zhao, H., 2022. Influence of particle size on diffuse particulate pollutants in combined sewer systems. *Sci. Total Environ.* 846, 157476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157476>.
- ISO, 2007a. *ISO 2591-1:1988, Test Sieving - Part 1: Methods Using Test Sieves of Woven Wire Cloth and Perforated Metal Plate*. American National Standards Institute, Geneva, Switzerland.
- ISO, 2007b. *ISO 13320-1:1999, Particle size analysis, Laser diffraction methods, Part 1: General principles*.
- Jeong, H., Choi, J.Y., Lee, J., Lim, J., Ra, K., 2020. Heavy metal pollution by road-deposited sediments and its contribution to total suspended solids in rainfall runoff from intensive industrial areas. *Environ. Pollut.* 115028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115028>.
- Kayhanian, M., McKenzie, E.R., Leatherbarrow, J.E., Young, T.M., 2012. Characteristics of road sediment fractionated particles captured from paved surfaces, surface run-off and detention basins. *Sci. Total Environ.* 439, 172–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.08.077>.
- Kinnell, P.I.A., 2022. Insights into the sediment transport processes operating in rain-impacted flows. *CATENA* 217, 106452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106452>.
- Lanzerstorfer, C., 2018. Heavy metals in the finest size fractions of road-deposited sediments. *Environ. Pollut.* 239, 522–531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.04.063>.
- Li, D., Hou, J., Zhou, Q., Lyu, J., Pan, Z., Wang, T., Sun, X., Yu, G., Tang, J., 2023a. Urban rainfall-runoff flooding response for development activities in new urbanized areas based on a novel distributed coupled model. *Urban Clim.* 51, 101628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2023.101628>.
- Li, L., Li, H., Zhao, H., 2023b. Modeling the wash-off of road-deposited sediments with different particle-sizes on asphalt and concrete roads. *J. Hydrol.* 625, 130115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.130115>.
- Li, H., Lv, J., He, X., Bao, Y., Nsabimana, G., 2024. Precipitation-dependent sensitivity of suspended sediment concentration to turbidity in a mountainous river in southwestern China. *Ecol. Indic.* 159, 111644. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111644>.
- Loganathan, P., Vigneswaran, S., Kandasamy, J., 2013. Road-deposited sediment pollutants: a critical review of their characteristics, source apportionment, and management. *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43, 1315–1348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2011.644222>.
- Malek Mohammadi, M., Najafi, M., Kermanshachi, S., Kaushal, V., Serajiantehrani, R., 2020. Factors influencing the condition of sewer pipes: state-of-the-art review. *Journal of Pipeline Systems Engineering and Practice* 11, 03120002. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)PS.1949-1204.0000483](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)PS.1949-1204.0000483).
- Martínez, G., García-Chevesich, P.A., Guillen, M., Tejada-Purizcana, T., Martínez, K., Ticona, S., Novoa, H.M., Crespo, J., Holley, E.A., McCray, J.E., 2024. Urban stormwater quality in Arequipa, southern Peru: an initial assessment. *Water* 16, 108. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16010108>.
- Mitchell, G., Oduyemi, K., Akunna, J., 2019. Road deposited sediment: implications for the performance of filter drains servicing strategic trunk roads. *Water Sci. Technol.* 80, 747–761. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2019.319>.
- Müller, A., Österlund, H., Marsalek, J., Viklander, M., 2020. The pollution conveyed by urban runoff: a review of sources. *Sci. Total Environ.* 709, 136125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.136125>.
- Muthanna, T.M., Viklander, M., 2019. Remobilization of sediments in gully pots during high intensity precipitation events. In: Mannina, G. (Ed.), *New Trends in Urban Drainage Modelling*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 993–996. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99867-1_171.
- Muthusamy, M., Tait, S., Schellart, A., Beg, M.N.A., Carvalho, R.F., de Lima, J.L.M.P., 2018. Improving understanding of the underlying physical process of sediment wash-off from urban road surfaces. *J. Hydrol.* 557, 426–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2017.11.047>.
- Naves, J., Rieckermann, J., Cea, L., Puertas, J., Anta, J., 2020. Global and local sensitivity analysis to improve the understanding of physically-based urban wash-off models from high-resolution laboratory experiments. *Sci. Total Environ.* 709, 136152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.136152>.
- Naves, Juan, Anta, J., Suárez, J., Puertas, J., 2020a. Hydraulic, wash-off and sediment transport experiments in a full-scale urban drainage physical model. *Sci Data* 7, 44. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0384-z>.
- Naves, Juan, Anta, J., Suárez, J., Puertas, J., 2020b. Development and calibration of a new drifter-based rainfall simulator for large-scale sediment wash-off studies. *Water* 12, 152. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12010152>.
- Naves, J., García, J.T., Puertas, J., Anta, J., 2021. Assessing different imaging velocimetry techniques to measure shallow runoff velocities during rain events using an urban drainage physical model. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 25, 885–900. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-25-885-2021>.
- Neupert, J.W., Lau, P., Venghaus, D., Barjenbruch, M., 2021. Development of a new testing approach for decentralised technical sustainable drainage systems. *Water* 13, 722. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13050722>.
- Rietveld, M., Clemens, F., Langeveld, J., 2020. Solids dynamics in gully pots. *Urban Water J.* 17, 669–680. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2020.1823430>.

- Rivers, E.N., Heitman, J.L., McLaughlin, R.A., Howard, A.M., 2021. Reducing roadside runoff: tillage and compost improve stormwater mitigation in urban soils. *J. Environ. Manage.* 280, 111732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111732>.
- Romero-Barreiro, M. del P., Pinilla-Castañeda, R.D., Zafra-Mejía, C.A., 2015. Evaluación temporal de la concentración de metales pesados (Pb y Cu) asociada con el sedimento vial: Fontibón-Barrios Unidos (Bogotá D. C., Colombia). *Ing. Univ.* 19, 315–333. <https://doi.org/10.1114/javeriana.iyu19-2.etcn>.
- Russell, K.L., Vietz, G.J., Fletcher, T.D., 2018. Urban catchment runoff increases bedload sediment yield and particle size in stream channels. *Anthropocene* 23, 53–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ancene.2018.09.001>.
- Russell, K.L., Vietz, G.J., Fletcher, T.D., 2019. Urban sediment supply to streams from hillslope sources. *Sci. Total Environ.* 653, 684–697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.374>.
- Rusydi, A.F., 2018. Correlation between conductivity and total dissolved solid in various type of water: a review. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* 118, 012019. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/118/1/012019>.
- dos Santos, P.R.S., Fernandes, G.J.T., Moraes, E.P., Moreira, L.F.F., 2019. Tropical climate effect on the toxic heavy metal pollutant course of road-deposited sediments. *Environ. Pollut.* 251, 766–772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.05.043>.
- Sañudo, E., Cea, L., Puertas, J., Naves, J., Anta, J., 2024. Large-scale physical facility and experimental dataset for the validation of urban drainage models. *Hydrol. Process.* 38, e15068. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.15068>.
- Schiff, K.C., Tiefenthaler, L.L., Bay, S.M., Greenstein, D.J., 2016. Effects of rainfall intensity and duration on the first flush from parking lots. *Water* 8, 320. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w8080320>.
- Shajib, M.T.I., Hansen, H.C.B., Liang, T., Holm, P.E., 2019. Metals in surface specific urban runoff in Beijing. *Environ. Pollut.* 248, 584–598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.02.039>.
- Shi, P., Arter, C., Liu, X., Keller, M., Schulin, R., 2017. Soil aggregate stability and size-selective sediment transport with surface runoff as affected by organic residue amendment. *Sci. Total Environ.* 607–608, 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.07.008>.
- Taylor, M., Elliott, H.A., Navitsky, L.O., 2018. Relationship between total dissolved solids and electrical conductivity in Marcellus hydraulic fracturing fluids. *Water Sci. Technol.* 77, 1998–2004. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2018.092>.
- Toranjian, A., Marofi, S., 2017. Evaluation of statistical distributions to analyze the pollution of Cd and Pb in urban runoff. *Water Sci. Technol.* 75, 2072–2082. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2017.054>.
- Vaze, J., Chiew, F.H.S., 2002. Experimental study of pollutant accumulation on an urban road surface. *Urban Water* 4, 379–389. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1462-0758\(02\)00027-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1462-0758(02)00027-4).
- Verbanck, M.A., Ashley, R.M., Bachoc, A., 1994. International workshop on origin, occurrence and behaviour of sediments in sewer systems: summary of conclusions. *Water Res.* 28, 187–194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354\(94\)90133-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354(94)90133-3).
- Viklander, M., 1998. Particle size distribution and metal content in street sediments. *Journal of Environmental Engineering* 124, 761–766. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9372\(1998\)124:8\(761\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9372(1998)124:8(761)).
- Wang, Q., Zhang, Q., Wu, Y., Wang, X.C., 2017. Physicochemical conditions and properties of particles in urban runoff and rivers: implications for runoff pollution. *Chemosphere* 173, 318–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.01.066>.
- Wang, J., Wei, H., Huang, J., He, T., Deng, Y., 2023. Soil aggregate stability and its response to overland runoff–sediment transport in karst peak–cluster depressions. *J. Hydrol.* 620, 129437. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2023.129437>.
- Wijesiri, B., Egodawatta, P., McGree, J., Goonetilleke, A., 2016. Understanding the uncertainty associated with particle-bound pollutant build-up and wash-off: a critical review. *Water Res.* 101, 582–596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.06.013>.
- Winston, R.J., Witter, J.D., Tirpak, R.A., 2023. Measuring sediment loads and particle size distribution in road runoff: implications for sediment removal by stormwater control measures. *Sci. Total Environ.* 902, 166071. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.166071>.
- Xue, H., Zhao, L., Liu, X., 2020. Characteristics of heavy metal pollution in road runoff in the Nanjing urban area, East China. *Water Sci. Technol.* 81, 1961–1971. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2020.249>.
- Yang, Q., Beecham, S., Liu, J., Pezzaniti, D., 2019. The influence of rainfall intensity and duration on sediment pathways and subsequent clogging in permeable pavements. *J. Environ. Manage.* 246, 730–736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.05.151>.
- Yarmoshenko, I., Malinovsky, G., Baglaeva, E., Seleznev, A., 2020. A landscape study of sediment formation and transport in the urban environment. *Atmosphere* 11, 1320. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11121320>.
- Zafra, C.A., Temprano, J., Tejero, I., 2008. Particle size distribution of accumulated sediments on an urban road in rainy weather. *Environ. Technol.* <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330801983532>.
- Zhao, H., Jiang, Q., Xie, W., Li, X., Yin, C., 2018. Role of urban surface roughness in road-deposited sediment build-up and wash-off. *J. Hydrol.* 560, 75–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.03.016>.
- Zhao, H., Ma, Y., Fang, J., Hu, L., Li, X., 2022. Particle size distribution and total suspended solid concentrations in urban surface runoff. *Sci. Total Environ.* 815, 152533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152533>.